

Preserving Cultural identity, behaving in intercultural settings

Kurbanova Sevara a teacher of
Andijan State of Foreign Language
Odilova Muattaroy a Student of
Andijan State of Foreign Language

Today there is an urgent need to develop a cultural approach to the construction of the theory and practice of social work, which is due not only to the traditional composite cultural image of Russia, but also complex processes of social and cultural dynamics of the XX century, during which disappears mandatory before the codification of society. structured hierarchy of existence, there is a multiplicity of cultural identity and the right to self-identification.

Russia - is a continent of ethnic groups, each with its inherent willows are symbolic representations of the system and the semantic relations. The Cultural competence involves knowledge of cultural technologies and symbolic objects, the ability to use this knowledge in their daily practice. How is it possible to take into account cultural factors. There are two aspects of cultural urological competencies: individual and institutional. Individual competence - a social worker understanding the distinctive features of culture (as its own. And clients) and their impact on the existential, psychological. philosophical, social features, on the semantic and behavioral organization of the continuum of everyday life. Institutional competence characterizes the cultural view of social awareness service and its ability to work in multicultural situations, adapting to cultural diversity.¹

At the end of the XX century in society coexistence of two (or more) cultures is not the only problem. Today's problem - a problem of the existence of the set of mixed and borderline forms of culture caused a total rejection of norms - social, ethical, aesthetic, linguistic. This principle the plurality of postmodern "forms of life" (L. Wittgenstein) is complicated in our country transgression of cultural matrices.

The growing interaction of cultures causes a significant change in the cultural forms of life (both at the national and at the local-group level), and in the language of everyday practice. The scale of the new information from the cultural environment, so intense, that may cause the representatives of culture - the recipient partial loss of cultural identity, in the extreme case - culture shock. The crisis of identity is always fraught with phenomena of marginalization, anomie deviance, psychopathology, etc. The tasks of social workers in this case are acculturation and cultural adaptation of clients not cope on their own with fast (or cardinal) cultural changes.

Therefore, you should understand the essence and the main stages of cultural adaptation, about the personal and cultural characteristics that deepen or mitigate a collision of an individual (or group) with the new socio-cultural reality. Ability to identify and prevent obsolete client cultural stereotypes, to help him take the new patterns, overcome, if necessary, rejection of new cultural traditions should be considered an important theoretical and practical skills.ⁱⁱ

It is important to emphasize that almost every one of the social groups - a group facing a problem of cultural adaptation. Migrants and refugees arriving in the new socio-cultural environment, people change social status due to change of profession, loss or gaining power, improvement or deterioration of the material conditions of life, teenagers and senior citizens, young people, called in the army or who came to serve on a contract basis, orphaned children, prisoners, members of deviant or delinquent groups, etc. - They are all more or less affected by the problems of inculturation in its various versions. So, for migrants it is a problem of initiation to the cultural patterns of the dominant society, so it is important to organize the social worker assimilation (in various forms) of typical behaviors, values and ways of cultural activity. Many people form groups with their unique subculture. Such, for example, soldiers, teenagers, groups of individuals with deviant behavior (prostitutes, drug addicts, vagrants, etc.). A social worker must not only know the specifics of such groups, the distinctive features of the subculture as a special sphere of culture, but in each case to decide whether it is necessary to help the individual to assimilate subcultural standards or adapt this subculture and its carriers into the mainstream culture.ⁱⁱⁱ

In our country, are experiencing a period of cultural transformations,

quality of life status and stratification accessories, ignorance of these rules cause problems on the personal level of identity, maladjustment, psychopathology, and the group - the problem of communicating and consolidation in the context of cultural change. Tasks cultural regulation should always be the focus of attention of the social worker as social work as an activity designed to, including, and regulate human coexistence. The liberalization of value-normative sphere does not cancel, but greatly complicates the work of integrating the social whole. The modern world is fundamentally unstable, it is full of conflicts and contradictions. Moreover, in the postmodern reality blurred opposition "center-periphery", "high-low", "individual-collective", "part of the whole," "presence-absence", etc. But reasonableness tolerance, relativism labyrinth must nevertheless comply with the principle of "minimum necessary solidarity" (AR Radcliffe-Brown).

References

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